

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION IN DIFFERENT COUNTRIES

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Abstract. *This article provides a comparative analysis of the preschool education system in different countries. The tasks set by the Western education system for pedagogy will be considered; they are based on a situational approach to the organization of the educational process, which orients pedagogy to the life situations that arise in children, thereby conducting training that is close to real life. The main characteristics of the situational approach are: complete interaction between play and the child's learning. Based on the situational analysis, the learning process is planned.*

Keywords: *comparative analysis, preschool education, concept, pedagogy, psychology, education.*

The concept of education determines the organization of a purposeful pedagogical process and the stimulation of an active personality aimed at obtaining a set of social experience. Preschool education is the education of preschool children in the family and kindergarten; a unique system of bringing the child's consciousness and behavior into conformity with the norms of the social environment. This is a process of personal development, which is aimed mainly at instilling in the child the culture accepted in a particular society. Preschool education should be aimed at the comprehensive development of the child and preparation for school life.

The tasks set by the Western education system for pedagogy are based on a situational approach to organizing the educational process, which orients pedagogy to the life situations that arise in children, thereby conducting training that is close to real life. The main characteristics of the situational approach are: complete interaction between play and the child's learning. Based on the situational analysis, the learning process is planned.

In connection with problems and changes in the development of the educational sphere, West Germany gave preference to new types of educational institutions. They imply the integration of joint education and training of mentally unbalanced and healthy children. Western education includes many projects aimed at improving it. In Germany, 20% of the preschool education system exists at the expense of the state, 80% at the expense of organizations. There is no single program. The main tasks facing educators are: to effectively contribute to the creation of a harmonious process of emotional, mental and physical development of students, to carry out the social development of children, to develop their skills of favorable behavior in society, to organize children's activities that will be aimed at studying and understanding the world around them, build fruitful relationships between parents and the educational community. institution.

Every German kindergarten teacher has the task of revealing the social inclinations of the child - they help the preschooler understand and express his "I". Sufficient attention is paid to the timely formation of such qualities as self-confidence, self-confidence and self-esteem. It is believed that, having such qualities, the child will be able to endure his failures more easily.

Rudolf Steiner put forward an idea based on processes that could lead a child to contact with the outside world, the development of his hidden abilities and properties. One of the first innovative methods in education is the “Maria Montessori school”. The Montessori system is used in preschool and school institutions in the UK, Australia, Germany, India, Holland, Canada, Italy, USA, Japan, and Switzerland.

Human personality is diverse in its structure and development. Each state must develop a flexible and detailed plan for the educational process used in preschool institutions. This will help bring people together more effectively without infringing on their foundations and traditions.

In Japan, kindergarten is not a compulsory educational stage. Children come here at the request of their parents - usually from the age of four. All kindergartens in Japan are private. In most kindergartens, the main task of teachers is to teach children to be obedient. Japanese home education is extremely gentle; children are rarely prohibited from doing anything. But towards strangers - on the street, in public places - Japanese tradition strictly requires expression of the utmost respect, including from small children. Therefore, a lot of time in kindergarten is devoted to teaching good manners and getting to know the ritual side of life. Children must master various etiquette formulas and know where and when to apply them. In Japan:

- purposeful education of leaders is practiced in kindergartens. Each child repeatedly becomes a leader. They vote for him; everyone expresses their opinion about him directly and openly;

- Great importance is attached to labor education. Here is what, for example, a 4-year-old child is required to do:

- attach an on-duty badge to yourself in the morning;

- check the number of children in the group;

- distribute materials for classes;

- when preparing for meals, wipe the tables, set them, serve those sitting at the table, remove the dishes after eating;

- before returning home, remove the duty badge and pass it on to the next one (without reminding the teacher). This is how organization is fostered. And 5-year-old children clean the kindergarten yard. Moreover, each child is engaged in this work for a total of 30 minutes. In Week;

- in Japanese kindergartens beauty and artistic education of children are valued. The decorative decoration attracts attention: the walls are often draped with rugs or colored fabrics, on which a child’s drawing can be easily attached. The design is dominated by a combination of clay, stone, wood, dead wood, and foam. In rooms and areas, paper or plastic lanterns, fish, and dragons hang and sway from the ceilings. Against this background, a variety of visual activities take place. Drawing classes are held not only at tables. Often they are transferred to sandboxes. Children draw hieroglyphs and images in the sand and then create dramatizations around it. It is extremely rare for teachers in the fine arts to use a model (as is very often done in our country). Instead, descriptions, riddle games, toys, children's movements, art objects and other illustrative material prevail.

The United States does not have a unified early childhood education system. It is organized within the framework of various short-term or long-term programs aimed at solving specific problems. A program is understood as a certain system of significant measures that operate to achieve a specific goal. Thus, in the USA there are various programs designed for preschoolers.

As a rule, these are programs aimed at reducing the impact of stress factors on children and ensuring their development.

All kindergartens in China are quite large and on average can accommodate up to 270 children, which fully meets the requirements of the state, due to severe overcrowding. At the same time, one kindergarten may follow a different schedule for each child individually. In kindergartens they began to teach against selfishness, where young children from the very first years are taught to be strict with themselves, control their own desires and be part of a team. All individual characteristics of children are not considered innate and are therefore not encouraged. The main task of kindergartens is to load children in such a way that there is no possibility of any unfavorable situations arising.

By the end of the First World War, preschools in England were clearly divided into those providing care, health and physical development (nurseries) and those promoting comprehensive development, learning and educational work (kindergartens and classrooms). In preschool institutions, an adult supports the child in learning, helping him to master and use the educational, developmental and cultural space around him to the maximum. It is important that the adult does not dominate, for example, when talking with a child, but that thoughts and feelings are exchanged and a state of mutual continuous mental activity is maintained. All three concepts influenced not only the historical development of English preschool education, but can also be traced in the formation of new approaches to the development of educational content at the present stage.

The emergence of so-called non-traditional educational institutions, alternative public schools, and kindergartens became the basis of the Russian educational system. They are characterized by such features as the specificity of the goals and content of education; voluntariness in the choice of an institution of a certain orientation by parents and their children; relative administrative independence; a special atmosphere and moral climate that contribute to better adaptation of the child and his multifaceted development.

Children in Western European countries usually attend a pre-school or kindergarten, which is supervised by the Ministry of Education, before starting compulsory education. Preschool education of a child begins at the age of 2.5 to 6 years, depending on the country (see table). Its duration depends on the age at which compulsory education begins.

In most countries, parents do not pay for preschool education because it is considered part of the school system, free until a certain age. Almost all children here attend preschool institutions (98-99%). In countries where parents are forced to pay for education, children's attendance is lower and therefore their level of development is lower when they enter primary school.

In Western European countries, serious attention is paid to the integration of children with disabilities into educational centers, play groups and preschool institutions. To do this, specialists in the field of the child's specific disease are brought in to help him, as well as additional staff to reduce the burden on permanent staff and train them to behave in difficult situations. Integration of children with disabilities is beneficial for their physical and physiological development and is also necessary for the development of communication skills.

In the Netherlands, for example, every small village has a playgroup. Because tuition fees are low, they are suitable even for families considered at risk. Many playgroups offer special programs for immigrant and refugee children to prepare them for preschool education.

In some countries, preschools offer hot lunches. In other countries, children take sandwiches with them. In countries where the school day is short, children usually eat lunch at

home. Children's centers sometimes provide a hot lunch, milk, fruit juices or tea, as well as fruit, and in some cases food is brought from home. Meals are not provided in playgroups, as children spend part of the day here. However, they may be offered drinks and fruit.

Table 1. Age groups in the preschool education system

A country	Age of onset		Duration preschool education	Attendance	Most %	School hours
	compulsory preschool	compulsory preschool education				
Austria	6	3	3	80	3	Half day
Belgium	6	2,5	3,5	95	3,5	Full day
Denmark	7	6	1	75	1	Half day
Germany	6	3	3	75	3	Half day
Ireland	6	4	2	56-99	2	Full day
Italy	6	3	3	90	3	Full day
Finland	7	7 0-7 Educational services	7 0-7 Educational services			Full day
France	6	6	3	3	90	Full day
Luxembourg	4	4	4	2	100	Full day
Netherlands	5	5	4	2	98	Full day
Portugal	6	6	3	3	50	Full day
Spain	6	6	3	3	90	Full day
Sweden	7	7	4	1	100	Half day
Great Britain	5	5	4	2	100	Full day

In conclusion, we note that the differences between kindergartens around the world are symbolic (focus on preparation for school, on the family or on the child). Preschool is the first place where a child finds his own identity, learns to interact with people outside his family, make new friends, thereby gaining self-confidence. Preschools can play a vital role in the development of a child's personality by positively shaping his attitude and abilities. More importantly, it can give the child the right motivation to learn by demonstrating that learning can be fun and interesting. It forms the first impression of the place of study.

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